
Derivative of AC recombination velocity of minority carriers as applied to the determination of the optimum base thickness of an (n+/p/p+) silicon solar cell

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Abstract This work is devoted to the determination of the optimum thickness of the base of the (n+/p/p+) silicon solar cell, front illuminated by the (n+) face by a monochromatic light in frequency modulation.

The method of the derivative of the expression of AC recombination velocity of minority carriers on the back side of the base is used for the first time, and allows to obtain results of the optimum base thickness as modulation frequency dependent. The base optimum thickness decreases with the frequency and makes it possible to envisage the realization of solar cells with a reduced base, for an economy of the raw material (Si).

Keywords Silicon Solar Cell –AC Recombination Velocity - Base Optimum Thickness

Introduction

Previous works of characterization of the solar cell, have been carried out using an electrical or optical signal, in modulation frequency (ω) [1-6], applied to the solar cell.

By solving the dynamically dynamic diffusion equation, relative to the density of the minority charge carriers in the base, the photocurrent density AC J_{ph} (S_f , S_b , $D(\omega)$, H , α) is obtained and allows to deduce the expression AC $S_b(D(\omega), H, \alpha)$ of the minority carriers recombination velocity at the rear face (p/p+) [7-11]. The graphic study of this expression as a function of the thickness (H), made it possible to deduce a technique for determining the optimum thickness of the base (H_{opt}) [12-22].

This work presents the determination of the optimum thickness of the base of the solar cell illuminated by its front face (n +), by the exploitation of the curve of $S_b(H, D(\omega), \alpha)$ [23-27] versus thickness (H), through the point (H_{opt}) of zero derivative.

Two expressions $F(H, D(\omega))$ and $G(H, D(\omega), \alpha)$, forming a transcendental equation [28-30], are deduced and, whose graphical representation leads to (H_{opt}), which is then modeled as a function of frequency and for an absorption coefficient (α) of high penetration [31, 32].

Theory

The solar cell considered is of type (n +/p/p +) [33, 34] whose structure is presented in figure.1, with (H) the base thickness.

Figure 1: Structure of a front illuminated (n+-p-p+) silicon solar cell.

Dynamic continuity equation

The continuity equation of the minority carriers in the base of solar cell under dynamic state [1-4], is of the form:

$$D(\omega) \times \frac{\partial^2 \delta(x,t)}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\delta(x,t)}{\tau} = -G(x, \omega, t) + \frac{\partial \delta(x,t)}{\partial t} \tag{1}$$

The complex relationships under dynamic state for both diffusion length and diffusion coefficient are follow:

$$\frac{1}{L(\omega)^2} = \frac{1}{L^2} \times (i\omega\tau + 1) \tag{2} \quad \text{and} \quad D(\omega) = D_0 \times \left(\frac{1 - j\omega^2\tau^2}{1 + (\omega\tau)^2} \right) \tag{3}$$

D0 is the diffusion coefficient and (τ) is the lifetime of the minority charge carriers, in the base under steady state.

G is the AC generation rate given by the following expression:

$$G(x,t) = g(x)\exp(i\omega t) \tag{4}$$

With g(x) the spatial component:

$$g_1(x) = \alpha I_0 (1 - R) [e^{-\alpha x}] \tag{5}$$

The monochromatic incident flux is (I0); the absorption coefficient is (α(λ)) and R(λ) is the reflection coefficient of the material at wavelength λ [31, 32].

Expression of the minority carriers density

The solution of equation (1) giving the minority carriers density in the base is:

$$\delta(x, \omega, \alpha) = A \cosh\left(\frac{x}{L(\omega)}\right) + B \sinh\left(\frac{x}{L(\omega)}\right) + C \cdot \exp(-\alpha x) \tag{6}$$

The C constant is dependent of the optical parameters.

Boundary conditions

To determine A and B the following boundary conditions are used:

At the junction, x=0

$$\left. \frac{\partial \delta(x, \alpha, \omega)}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} = \frac{Sf}{D} \delta(0, \omega, \alpha) \tag{7}$$

At the back surface, $x = H$:

$$\left. \frac{\partial \delta(x, \omega, \alpha)}{\partial x} \right)_{x=H} = -\frac{Sb}{D} \delta(H, \omega, \alpha) \quad (8)$$

Sf and Sb denote the minority carriers' recombination velocity [35-43] at the junction and rear side of the base, respectively.

Expression of photocurrent density

The photocurrent density is then deduced from minority carriers density and given by the following expression as:

$$J_{ph}(Sf, Sb, \alpha, H, \omega) = qD(\omega) \left. \frac{\partial \delta(x, Sf, Sb, \alpha, H, \omega)}{\partial x} \right)_{x=0} \quad (9)$$

q is the charge of the electron.

Expression of the recombination velocity of minority carriers on the back side of the base

The profile of the curves of variation of the density of the photocurrent as a function of recombination velocity at the junction show that at Sf large values, each curve has a horizontal step, regardless of modulation frequency. The gradient of the photocurrent with respect to (Sf) is zero [44, 45]:

$$\frac{\partial J_{ph}(Sf, Sb, \alpha, H, \omega)}{\partial Sf} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Solving this equation allows us to obtain the following expressions of minority carriers recombination velocity at the rear side of the base of the solar cell, expressed as:

$$S_{b1}(H, \omega) = -\frac{D(\omega)}{L(\omega)} \frac{sh\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right)}{ch\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right)} \quad (11)$$

$$S_{b2}(\alpha, H, \omega) = D(\omega) \frac{\alpha \left(ch\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right) - e^{-\alpha H} \right) - \frac{1}{L(\omega)} sh\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right)}{\left(ch\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right) - e^{-\alpha H} - \alpha L(\omega) sh\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right) \right)} \quad (12)$$

We propose a method for determining the optimum thickness of the base of the solar cell, through the study of the expression of the minority carriers recombination velocity on the rear side of the base.

Thus, the curve of Sb2 versus (H) [23-27], have an optimum. Then the derivative at the point of optimum recombination velocity of Sb2 with respect to H is zero:

$$\frac{\partial S_{b2}(\alpha, H, \omega)}{\partial H} = 0 \quad (13)$$

It then comes:

$$\tanh\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right) = \frac{1}{L(\omega)\alpha} \left[\frac{1}{e^{-\alpha H} ch\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right)} - 1 \right] \quad (14)$$

This transcendental equation is broken down into two functions for graphical resolution [28-30] as:

$$F(H, \omega, \alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha L(\omega)} \left[\frac{1}{e^{-\alpha H} ch\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right)} - 1 \right] \quad (15)$$

$$G(H, \omega) = \tanh\left(\frac{H}{L(\omega)}\right) \quad (16)$$

Results and Discussions

Graphic resolution

Figure 2, gives the representation of the two expressions $F(H,\omega,\alpha)$ and $G(H,\omega)$ on a vertical bicurve scale as a function of (H) , for given modulation frequency (ω) and keeping the absorption coefficient constant.

Figure 2: Profile of G and F as a function of base thickness for different frequency values and $\alpha = 6.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The intercept point of the two curves gives the optimum thickness (H_{opt}) for a chosen modulation frequency (ω). Thus Table 1 shows all the H_{opt} values as a function of dynamic diffusion coefficient and the modulation frequency (ω).

Table 1: Values of the optimum thickness, as a function of D and ω .

$\omega(\text{rad.s}^{-1})$	10^2	10^3	10^4	2.10^4	3.10^4	4.10^4	5.10^4	6.10^4	7.10^4	8.10^4	9.10^4
$D(\omega)(\text{cm}^2/\text{s})$	35	34.9965	34.6535	33.6538	32.1101	30.1724	28.0000	25.7353	23.4899	21.3415	19.3370
$H_{opt} \text{ (cm)}$	0.0101	0.0101	0.0101	0.0099	0.0097	0.0094	0.0092	0.0089	0.0085	0.0082	0.0078

From the table above, we produce the representation (**Fig. 3**) of the optimum thickness as function of dynamic diffusion coefficient $D(\omega)$ of the minority carriers in the base.

Figure 3: Optimum thickness profile versus dynamic diffusion coefficient

The expression in modeling of the optimum thickness (Hopt) as a function of minority carriers diffusion coefficient in the base, is given by the following equation:

$$Hopt(cm) = 1.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \times D(cm^2 \cdot s^{-1}) + 0.0052 \tag{17}$$

Figure 4 and 5 produce the Hopt curve as function of (ω).

Figure 4: Optimum thickness profile as a function of modulation frequency

The following expression gives the mathematical modeling of (Hopt), which is a decreasing function of the modulation frequency (ω):

$$Hop(cm) = -1,8 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot \omega^2 - 10^{-8} \cdot \omega + 0,01 \tag{18}$$

Figure 5: Histogram of optimum thickness as a function of frequency

The optimal thickness is large at low frequencies, corresponding to the static regime ($\omega\tau \ll 1$) of the solar cell. In this low frequency interval, the relaxation time of minority carriers is important (D large values), allowing a large distance (Einstein's relation), so a large base thickness is usable [17].

At high frequency values, the relaxation time of minority carriers is reduced ($\omega\tau \gg 1$), corresponding to a short travel distance, then the optimum thickness needed to collect carriers should be low [20, 21, 46].

Other works [46-53] corroborate the above results, showing the decrease in the optimum thickness of the silicon solar cell base, when subjected to:

- Monochromatic light with constant flux absorption coefficient ($\alpha(\lambda)$) [17, 47].
- Monochromatic light $\alpha(\lambda)$ in frequency modulation (ω) [20, 21, 46].
- Constant magnetic field B [18, 19, 50].
- Irradiation with charged particles flux [52].
- Modification of base doping rate [16, 46].
- Effect of temperature [22, 48, 49, 53].

Studies wafers [54-58] of silicon for different thicknesses, do not guarantee the reproducibility of electronic parameters and however only compare the results of macroscopic parameters.

Conclusion

A new technique for determining the optimum thickness of the base of n+/p/p+, silicon solar cell under monochromatic illumination ($\alpha(\lambda)$), in frequency modulation (ω), was presented, through the analysis of the curve of ($Sb_2(H, D(\omega), \alpha)$) the recombination velocity of minority charge carriers on the rear side. The optimum thickness (H_{opt}) of the solar cell base, is deduced from the curves of the expressions (transcendental equations) obtained from the derivative of $Sb(\alpha, H, \omega)$ with respect to (H). The H_{opt} thickness is modeled as a decreasing function of the frequency (ω), and increasing one with dynamic diffusion coefficient, for a given value of the absorption coefficient (α) of high penetration into the base. The importance of the thickness of the base in the manufacture of the solar cell, with a view to optimizing the amount of usable material, is economically undeniable, and also leads to an improvement in the photo conversion efficiency.

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